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A GROUNDED THEORY OF THE REQUIREMENTS ENGINEERING PROCESS

Layla Alfawzan¹ and Alphonso Bellamy²

¹Eastern Michigan University, USA

²College of Technology, Eastern Michigan University, Ypsilanti, MI 48197

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the requirements engineering (RE) process by conducting interviews with RE professionals and applying grounded theory to determine whether a theory of RE emerges. Analysis of the interviews revealed prominent data patterns that were used to model the RE process. The model depicts the RE process as one of establishing a match through discovery and streamlining, and which utilizes corrective measures in order to manage threats to establishing a match. The process involves many entities but is mainly conducted by RE professionals whose experience plays a major role in extracting complete requirements and detecting occasions of mismatch between customer needs and the software requirements, which represent their main concern during the process.

This paper contributes to the empirical analysis of RE by presenting evidence of the RE process in its basic form as carried out in industry, which may form as a building block for further RE research.

KEYWORDS

Requirements engineering, Grounded theory & Empirical software engineering

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An Analysis Of Software Requirements Specification Characteristics In Regulated Environments

Johnny Marques and Sarasuaty Yelisetty

Computer Science Division, Aeronautics Institute of Technology, Sao Jose dos Campos, Brazil

ABSTRACT

Requirements Engineering is the set of activities involved in creation, managing, documenting, and maintaining a requirements' set for a product. Engineering involves the use of systematic repeatability techniques to ensure that the Software Requirements are complete, consistent, valid, and verifiable. Software Requirements Specification is an organized process oriented toward defining, documenting and maintaining requirements throughout the development life cycle. Many authors suggest that requirements should always focus their claims on what the software product needs to address, without specifying how to implement them. However, the detail of Software Requirements is influenced by several factors such as: organizational thinking; existing specification standards; and regulatory needs. This work fits exactly with regulatory needs, where the characteristics of Software Requirements Specification in Regulated Environments such as aeronautics, railways and medical are presented and explored. This paper presents and analysis of software requirements specification characteristics in regulated environments. The four characteristics identified are: consistency (internal and external), unambiguity, verifiability, and traceability. The paper also describes the three standards used in these regulated environments (RTCA DO-178C, IEC 62279 and IEC 62304) and examines their similarities and differences from a Requirements Specification standpoint. The similarities and differences will be used to address a future requirements framework universal process that can be configured to address each standard by the usage of Software Process Lines.

KEYWORDS

Software, Requirements, Certification, Standards

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AUTHORS

Johnny Marques Was Born In Toronto, Canada, In 1977, But Has Been Living In Brazil Since 1986. He Received The B.Sc. In Computer Engineering From University Of The State Of Rio De Janeiro (UERJ), The M.Sc. (In Aeronautical Engineering) And A Phd. (In Electronic And Computer Engineering) Both From Aeronautics Institute Of Technology (ITA). He Is A Current A Professor In The Aeronautics Institute Of Technology (ITA). He Worked At EMBRAER In Software Processes Definition For 15 Years And Has Experience In Standards Used For Airborne Systems And Software Such As DO-178C, DO-254, ARP-4754, And DO- 200B. He Is Also Part Of Several Committees In IEEE Standards Association.

Sarasuaty Yelisetty Was Born In Sao Jose Dos Campos, Sao Paulo, Brazil. She Received The B.Sc. In Computer Engineering From University Of Vale Do Paraiba (UNIVAP). She Received The M.Sc. In Computer And Electronic Engineering From Aeronautics Institute Of Technology (ITA). Currently, She Is A Phd Student At ITA. Additionally, She Has Been Working At EMBRAER During The Last 10 Years And Has Experience In Standards Used For Airborne System And Software Certification.

Understanding The Characteristics, Benefits And Challenges Of Agile It Project Management: A Literature Based Perspective

Godfred Yaw Koi-Akrofi¹, Joyce Koi-Akrofi² and Henry Akwetey Matey³

^{1,3}Department of IT Studies, University of Professional Studies, Accra

²PMO Department, Vodafone Ghana

ABSTRACT

The objectives of this study was to bring out the understanding of the concept of agile IT project management; what it is and what it is not. It was also aimed at comparing the pros and cons of both agile and traditional methods of IT project management in a typical industry setting; the challenges of going purely agile, and so on. It is purely a review of literature of peer reviewed papers sourced mainly from Google Scholar. It was revealed that agile outweigh the traditional methods in terms of benefits, but its implementation poses a lot of challenges due to a number of issues, paramount among them being organizational culture and empowerment of the project team. This has resulted in a number of industries sticking to the traditional methods despite the overwhelming benefits of agile. In another school of thought, the combination of the two paradigms is the way forward.

KEYWORDS

Project Management, Scrum, Agile, Software, Traditional

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Analysis Of Gamification Elements To Explore Misinformation Sharing Based On U&G Theory: A Software Engineering Perspective

Malik Malki and Amin Shaqrah

College of Computer Science & Engineering in Yanbu- Taibah University, Medina,
Saudi Arabia

ABSTRACT

Gamification elements provide a personal drive to urge user experience, emotion, fun, and engagement, positively or negatively. These gamification elements may have been unintentionally employed through the design and implementation process of social media platforms to encourage users' behaviour towards misinformation sharing. This study intends to answer the subsequent question "What are the mostly used gamification elements that could possibly encourage users to share misinformation on social media platforms?". The study empirically investigates the usage of gamification elements and their relation to U&G theory with 286 participants. The results indicated that gamification elements usage scored high with regard to the self-expression perspective (frequency=216), as well as the interaction & collaborations perspective (frequency=198). Whereas, the information seeking perspective scored low (frequency=59) and leaderboard were the least usage (frequency=43). The results may be useful to guide software engineering, developers, GUI specialists to cater for design elements settings and their possible negative effects in social media contexts.

KEYWORDS

Online misinformation, Gamification elements, Software engineering, UGT.

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AUTHORS

Malik Malkiis an Assistant Professor of Software Engineering at the College of Science and Computer Engineering, Taibah University, Yanbu. He received his BSc in Computer Science from Taif University, KSA, in 2008 and his MSc in Advanced Software Engineering from Leicester University, UK, in 2011. He also received a PhD in Software Engineering from Bournemouth University, UK, in 2015. His research is focused on the engineering of social informatics, i.e., the systematic design of software- based solutions taking into consideration their interactions with related institutional and cultural contexts.

Amin Shaqrah is currently Associate Professor of Information Systems at Taibah University\Saudi Arabia. Shaqrah received his PhD in MIS from University of Banking & Financial Sciences and received MA in MIS from Amman Arab University for Graduate Studies. He had a leadership role in the design and implementation of MIS program at the undergraduate/graduate level. He is affiliated with several International professional societies on knowledge management, E-business, and a member of editorial review boards for a number of International Journals. His research interests include knowledge sharing and transfer, CRM value strategies, IT/IS adoption, human and social implications of enterprise systems (KM, CRM, and BI). His research work has appeared in several leading International Journals and conferences.

Introducing Refined Agile Model (Ram) In The Context Of Bangladesh's Software Development Environment Concentrating On The Improvement Of Requirement Engineering Process

Nirjhor Anjum¹ and Anwarul Kabir²

¹Chief Analyst Officer, REVE Systems, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

²Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science, American International University Bangladesh.

ABSTRACT

The Software Companies of Bangladesh are using different types of agile models for software development. Although theoretically these models are worthy for small and medium projects, in practical case they are not so effective. In doing so, this paper tries to find out why do the agile models not suitable for Bangladesh's Software Companies and how do the problems that the Software Companies face for using the models can be solved. To reveal the answers, this study is based on survey and interview methods. Findings of this paper show that Bangladesh's Software Companies are facing different problems for implementing traditional agile models, such as, Communicational gap, lack of Documentation, unavailability of Prototype, Customer's lack of knowledge in the area of IT and many more. The study shows that if the Requirement Engineering Process is perfectly managed and some rules are modified in the traditional agile models, these problems can be solved. In doing so, a new model has been proposed by the study named Refined Agile Model (RAM) which is claimed to be better for Bangladesh rather than the traditional Agile Models. This model proposes a process flow which consists of Prototyping Cycle, Development Iteration Cycle and Additional Development Iteration Cycle. This new model also ensures a Requirement Engineer at Client End, sufficient documentation, preparation of prototype and presentation of frequent Demos. After ensuring these requirements in several real time projects, it was found that those projects were completed more effectively compared to all other old project experiences. Eventually, the paper concludes by mentioning that the Refined Agile Model (RAM) is the best model in the Bangladeshi software environment.

KEYWORDS

Agile methodology, Requirement engineering process, Software development life cycle.

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A Literature Survey Of Cognitive Complexity Metrics For State chart Diagrams

Ann Wambui King'ori^{1, 2}, Geoffrey Muchiri Muketha¹ and Elyjoy Muthoni Micheni³

¹School of Computing and Information Technology, Murang'a University of Technology, Kenya

²Department of Information Communication Technology, Nkabune Technical Training Institute, Kenya

³School of Business and Management Sciences, The Technical University of Kenya, Kenya

ABSTRACT

Statechart diagrams have inherent complexity which keeps increasing every time the diagrams are modified. This complexity poses problems in comprehending statechart diagrams. The study of cognitive complexity has over the years provided valuable information for the design of improved software systems. Researchers have proposed numerous metrics that have been used to measure and therefore control the complexity of software. However, there is inadequate literature related to cognitive complexity metrics that can apply to measure statechart diagrams. In this study, a literature survey of statechart diagrams is conducted to investigate if there are any gaps in the literature. Initially, a description of UML and statechart diagrams is presented, followed by the complexities associated with statechart diagrams and finally an analysis of existing cognitive complexity metrics and metrics related to statechart diagrams. Findings indicate that metrics that employ cognitive weights to measure statechart diagrams are lacking.

KEYWORDS

UML, Statechart diagrams, Software metrics, Cognitive complexity metrics, statechart complexity metrics

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AUTHORS

Ann Wambui King'ori is an ICT Assistant Lecturer at the Department of Information Communication Technology at Nkabune Technical Training Institute, Kenya. She earned her Bachelor of Technology Education (Computer Studies) from the University of Eldoret, Kenya in 2014. She is currently pursuing her MSc. in Information Technology at Murang'a University of Technology, Kenya. Her research interests include software metrics, software quality, and business intelligence.

Geoffrey Muchiri Muketha is an Associate Professor and Dean of the School of Computing and Information Technology, Murang' a University of Technology, Kenya. He received his BSc. in Information Science from Moi University in 1995, his MSc. in Computer Science from Periyar University, India in 2004, and his Ph.D. in Software Engineering from Universiti Putra Malaysia in 2011. He has wide experience in teaching and supervision of postgraduate students. His research interests include software and business process metrics, software quality, verification and validation, empirical methods in software engineering, and component-based software engineering. He is a member of the International Association of Engineers (IAENG).

Elyjoy Muthoni Micheni is a Senior Lecturer in Information Systems in the Department of Management Science and Technology at The Technical University of Kenya. She holds a Ph.D. (Information Technology) from Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, Master of Science (Computer Based Information Systems) from Sunderland University, (UK); Bachelor of Education from Kenyatta University; Post Graduate Diploma in Project Management from Kenya Institute of Management. She has taught Management Information System courses for many years at the University level. She has presented papers in scientific conferences and has many publications in refereed journals. She has also co-authored a book for Middle-level colleges entitled: "Computerized Document Processing". Her career objective is to tap computer-based knowledge as a tool to advance business activities, promote research in ICT and enhance quality service.

Software Requirement Change Effort Estimation Model Prototype Tool For Software Development Phase

Jalal Shah¹, Nazri Kama², Nur Azaliah A Bakar², Zuhaibuddin Bhutto¹ and Sohrab Khan¹

¹Department of Computer System Engineering & Sciences Balochistan, University of Engineering & Technology Khuzdar, Pakistan

²Department of Advanced Informatics, Razak Faculty of Technology and Informatics, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

ABSTRACT

In software development phase software artifacts are not in consistent states such as: some of the class artifacts are fully developed some are half developed, some are major developed, some are minor developed and some are not developed yet. At this stage allowing too many software requirement changes may possibly delay in project delivery and increase development budget of the software. On the other hand rejecting too many changes may increase customer dissatisfaction. Software change effort estimation is one of the most challenging and important activity that helps software project managers in accepting or rejecting changes during software development phase. This paper extends our previous works on developing a software requirement change effort estimation model prototype tool for the software development phase. The significant achievements of the tool are demonstrated through an extensive experimental validation using several case studies. The experimental analysis shows improvement in the estimation accuracy over current change effort estimation models.

KEYWORDS

Software Change Effort Estimation, Software Requirement Changes, Change Impact Analysis and Software Development Phase.

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AUTHORS

Jalal Shah, He is an Assistant Professor at Balochistan University of Engineering & Technology Khuzdar Pakistan. He graduated in Bachelor of Computer System Engineering from Balochistan University of Engineering & Technology Khuzdar Pakistan. Later, he obtained a Master Degree from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM) in Software Engineering. In 2018, he received a Doctorate in Software Engineering from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM).

Nazri Kama, He is an Associate Professor at Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM) specializing in software engineering. He graduated in Bachelor in Management Information System from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. Later, he obtained a Master Degree from the same university in Real-time Software Engineering. In 2011, he received a Doctorate in Software Engineering from the University of Western Australia in Australia.

Nur Azaliah Abu Bakar, PhD is a Senior Lecturer at Advanced Informatics Department, Razak Faculty of Technology and Informatics, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. She graduated with a Bachelor (Information Technology) in Information Systems Engineering from Multimedia University (MMU) Malaysia (2000). She then obtained her Masters in Information Technology from Universiti Teknologi Mara (UiTM) in 2004. In 2017 she was awarded a Doctor of Philosophy degree in Information Technology (Enterprise Architecture) by Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM).

Zohibuddin Bhutto He is an Assistant Professor at Balochistan University of Engineering & Technology Khuzdar and pursuing his PhD degree from South Korea. He graduated in Bachelor of Software Engineering from Mehran University of Engineering & Technology Jamshoro Pakistan. Later, he obtained a Master Degree from Mehran University of Engineering & Technology Jamshoro Pakistan in IT.

Sohrab Khan. He is an Assistant Professor at Balochistan University of Engineering and Technology Khuzdar, specializing in information systems. He graduated in Bachelor's in Computer Engineering from Sir Syed University of Engineering and Technology Karachi. Later he obtained a Master Degree from Stockholm University Sweden in Computer and System Sciences. In 2019, he received a Doctorate degree from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM).

Developing And Implementing A Web-Based Recycling System For Protecting The Green Environment

DalalSaeed Al-Omairi, WejdanHamadAlNasheri, WaadYahya Al-Qarni, Ibrahim Almarashdeh, Mutasem k. Alsmadi, MuneerahAlshabanah and DaniahAlrajhi

Department Of Management Information Systems, College of Applied Studies and Community Service, Imam Abdurrahman Bin Faisal University, Al-Dammam, Saudi Arabia

ABSTRACT

Our society suffers a lot from the things that are thrown uselessly; these things may be beneficial to our society. On the other hand, communities suffer a lot of waste especially plastic waste; this has led to environmental pollution and depletion of natural resources. Therefore, this research aims to achieve sustainable development and achieve part of the Saudi Arabia vision 2030. Hence we have distributed a questionnaire to 88 responders, and based on the results of this study, which shows the importance of recycling and its impact on the environment and the extent of community interest in this subject and their supporters, The Let's Recycle site, based on the results of the questionnaire, will improve waste and plastics disposal in an environmentally positive manner. The proposed system was developed using the Unified Modelling Language (UML) and Microsoft Visual Studio2010 programming language.

KEYWORDS

Recycling System, Green Environment, Technology, Software Engineering and Unified Modelling Language.

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Evaluation Of Models To Implement The Iso 9001 Process Approach

Nuha El-Khalili

Department of Software Engineering, University of Petra, Amman, Jordan

ABSTRACT

The ISO 9001 standard is adopted worldwide by organizations from different sectors. The ISO 9001:2015 guidelines for implementing the process approach require not only the identification of the organization processes, but also the description of their interactions as a network system. Flow charts are a common tool adopted in quality management to show the sequence flow of a process. However, they do not show interrelations between different processes. The first aim of this study is to investigate the utilization of some software engineering models to satisfy the process approach requirement in the ISO 9001:2015 standard. The second aim is to show the implementation of the ISO 9001:2015 process approach and the "Plan-Do- Check-Act" (PDCA) cycle to manage academic programs processes as a case study and to present how the proposed models can be utilized to describe the interactions between processes. Finally, the study used a semi-structured interview methodology to evaluate the proposed models based on three criteria: understandability, modifiability and process improvement.

KEYWORDS

ISO 9001:2015; process approach; Software engineering models; Academic Program Management; semi-structured interview

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Requirements Variability Specification For Data Intensive Software

Eman Muslah and Said Ghoul

Faculty of Information Technology, Research Laboratory on Bio-inspired Software Engineering, Philadelphia University, Amman, Jordan

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the use of feature modeling technique, in software requirements specification, increased the variation support in Data Intensive Software Product Lines (DISPLs) requirements modeling. It is considered the easiest and the most efficient way to express commonalities and variability among different products requirements. Several recent works, in DISPLs requirements, handled data variability by different models which are far from real world concepts. This, led to difficulties in analyzing, designing, implementing, and maintaining this variability. However, this work proposes a software requirements specification methodology based on concepts more close to the nature and which are inspired from genetics. This bio-inspiration has carried out important results in DISPLs requirements variability specification with feature modeling, which were not approached by the conventional approaches. The feature model was enriched with features and relations, facilitating the requirements variation management, not yet considered in the current relevant works. The use of genetics-based methodology seems to be promising in data intensive software requirements variability specification.

KEYWORDS

Requirements variability specification, Data intensive software product lines, Bio-inspired modeling, data versions, feature model.

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